

Thomas Sydenham on scurvy (1685)

Summary by James Lind (1772)

This is James Lind's English summary of a text on scurvy by Sydenham in 1685, the original is in Latin.

Thomas Sydenham, the English Hippocrates

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=573>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_Sydenham

<https://history.rcp.ac.uk/inspiring-physicians/thomas-sydenham>

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<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

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The text below is from Lind (1772; 3rd ed) p.382-385.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/382/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/382/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216006&seq=406>

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1685

Thomæ Sydenham opera universa.

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The author has no where treated expressly of this disease, but in a posthumous work ascribed to him.¹ There the scurvy is said to be accompanied with, 1. spontaneous lassitude; 2. heaviness; 3. difficulty of breathing, especially after exercise; 4. rottenness of the gums; 5. fœtid breath; 6. frequent bleeding at the nose; 7. difficulty of walking; 8. a swelling sometimes, at other times a wasting of the legs; on which spots always appear, that are either livid, or of a leaden, yellow, or purple colour; 9. a sallow complexion. For cure, eight ounces of blood are to be taken from the arm, provided there be no sign of a dropsy; next morning a purging potion is to be given, and repeated twice, at the interval of three days betwixt each dose. On the intermediate days the

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antiscorbutic medicines are to be used, and continued for a month or two. But the more genuine sentiments of this candid author are to be found in his other works.

Cap. 4. de febribus continuis, ann. 1661, 62, 63, 64, he observes, that the two great subterfuges of ignorant physicians, were malignity and the scurvy; which they blamed for disorders and symptoms often owing to their own ill management. Thus, whatever bad and irregular symptoms have been brought on in fevers, perhaps by their unseasonable evacuations, these they ascribe to the malignity of the disease; but if the long continuance of the distemper should wipe off this aspersion of malignity, whatever afterwards obstructs the cure must be the scurvy; both of which are blamed without reason.

Sect. 6. cap. 5. de rheumatismo. To deliver my sentiments freely, though I do not

at all doubt that the scurvy is to be met with in these northern countries, yet I am persuaded it is not so frequent as generally supposed. For most of those disorders we term *scorbutic*, are the effects of approaching ills

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not yet formed into diseases, or the relics of some disease imperfectly cured. Thus, for instance, where a matter suited to produce the gout is newly generated, there appear various symptoms, which occasion us to suspect the scurvy; till the formation and actual appearance of the gout remove all doubt concerning the distemper. And in the same manner, many symptoms ascribed to the scurvy afflict gouty people after the fit is over, especially if it has been improperly treated. And this is to be understood not only of the gout, but also of the dropsy.

The proverb is, That where the scurvy ends, there the dropsy² begins; which is to be understood in this sense, that, upon the appearance of the dropsy, the preconceived opinion of the scurvy falls to the ground.

And the same may be said of several other chronic diseases that are but forming, and others that are not totally cured. He however thinks, there is a species of rheumatism near akin to the scurvy in its capital symptoms, and which requires the same method of cure. The pains shift from one place to another; rarely occasion a swelling; there is no fever; but it is attended with irregular symptoms; such especially as have taken much of the *Peruvian* bark are subject to it. Though it is otherwise a very obstinate disease, yet it may be effectually cured by the use of the antiscorbutic electuary

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before-mentioned, and a water distilled from scurvygrass, brooklime, cresses, &c.

1 *Processus integri in morbis ferè omnibus curandis.*

https://archive.org/details/b30325663_0002/page/n219/mode/2up

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/ynmh3pmk/items?canvas=115>

https://books.google.fi/books/about/Processus_integri_in_morbis_fere_omnibus.html?id=C8AaynwnPDIC

2 Dropsy. The historical diagnosis of dropsy – which is now obsolete – indicated simply an abnormal accumulation of fluid. The word derives from the Greek *hydrops* (water).

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CHOL9780521332866.101>

Dropsy. An ancient medical term used to indicate different conditions including chronic heart failure.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2017.07.104>

Scurvy can cause heart failure, so scurvy does not need to “end” if there is heart failure, eg.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-024-02941-x>